

CURRICULUM INTEGRATION IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING USING CDIO: GENERAL APPROACH

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Abstract

This paper is Part One of a 2-part submission to ISATE2013. It introduces the approach taken by the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) of Singapore Polytechnic to design an integrated curriculum for its 3-year program. It firstly presents a literature overview of the need for curriculum integration, followed by a summary of current approaches to curriculum integration. It explains the CDIO Standard 3 “Integrated Curriculum” and demonstrates that this approach is consistent with the nature of engineering practice which is an integrative process in practice. It outlines the various approaches taken by DCHE to integrate both technical content and CDIO skills into various core modules. The paper further argues that current approaches, while appeared effective as far as CDIO skills are concerned; are not satisfactory in terms of technical knowledge. Of key focus, it points out that present “traditional” approach that requires students to complete 2 projects (*Final Year Project* and *Plant Design Project*), is also inadequate. Alternatively it proposes the use of selected core modules in Year 3 that are “integrative” in nature to further strengthen the curriculum integration effort. Key issues and challenges are outlined, including the use of different pedagogies such as problem-based learning, which are not “mainstream” in chemical engineering education. Part Two deals with a specific example of curriculum integration using this “integrative” approach in a core module, ‘*Process Instrumentation and Control*’, in Year 3 and is presented by the second author in a separate paper for ISATE2013.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, CDIO, curriculum integration*

Introduction

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) in Singapore Polytechnic (SP) adopted CDIO (www.cdio.org) as the organizing education framework for a major curriculum redesign initiative in 2007. Various CDIO skills such as teamwork and communication, personal skills and attitudes (e.g. critical and creative thinking, managing learning, holding multiple perspectives, etc) have been integrated

into the curriculum (Cheah et al, 2013). This paper summarizes the general approach undertaken by the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) to design a curriculum for its 3-year program that integrates these CDIO skills alongside technical contents, that includes using selected core modules in Year 3 to supplement “traditional” approaches of curriculum integration using capstone projects.

Literature Review on Curriculum Integration

Firstly, what do we mean by “curriculum”? It came from the Latin word “currere” which means “*race course, to run, run way*”; referring to the course of deeds and experiences through which children grow to become mature adults. In the modern context, Connelly and Clandinin (1988) offered the following broad definition:

“Curriculum is often taken to mean a course of study. When we set our imagination free from the narrow notion that a course of study is a series of textbooks or specific outline of topics to be covered and objectives to be attained, broader more meaningful notions emerge. A curriculum can become one’s life course of action. It can mean the paths we have followed and the paths we intend to follow. In this broad sense, curriculum can be viewed as a person’s life experience.”

Secondly, what constitute an “integrated curriculum”? There are many definitions for integrated curriculum, as well as other terms that are often used synonymously, one of which is interdisciplinary curriculum. Venville and Dawson (2004) suggest that it is not an easy question to answer due to the diversity of approaches that currently exist. CDIO Standard 3 explains an “Integrated Curriculum” as follows (Crawley et al, 2007):

“A curriculum designed with mutually supporting disciplinary subjects, with an explicit plan to integrate personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills”

This is supplemented by a description that reads: “A CDIO curriculum includes learning experiences that lead to the acquisition of personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills (Standard 2), integrated with the learning of disciplinary content. Disciplinary subjects are mutually supporting when they

make explicit connections among related and supporting content and learning outcomes. An explicit plan identifies ways in which the integration of CDIO skills and multidisciplinary connections are to be made, for example, by mapping CDIO learning outcomes to courses and co-curricular activities that make up the curriculum". Supporting integrated curriculum is CDIO Standard 7 "Integrated Learning Experiences" which are "pedagogical approaches that foster the learning of disciplinary knowledge simultaneously with personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills. They incorporate professional engineering issues in contexts where they coexist with disciplinary issues."

The CDIO approach resonates well with the view of Malloy (1996), who sees a curriculum as "a potent tool for reform when it integrates and inter-relates subjects and disciplines in a manner that makes learning experiences meaningful". The CDIO approach is also consistent with another view of curriculum espoused by Shoemaker (1989) as quoted in Lake (1994): "... education that is organized in such a way that it cuts across subject matter lines, bringing together various aspects of the curriculum into meaningful association to focus upon broad areas of study. It views learning and teaching in a holistic way and reflects the real world, which is interactive".

The Need for Curriculum Integration

The need for curriculum integration is best summed up by Sheppard et al (2008) who noted that: "Although engineering education is strong on imparting some kind of knowledge, it is not very effective in preparing students to integrate their knowledge, skills and identity as developing professionals ... The tradition of putting theory before practice and the effort to cover technical knowledge comprehensively allow little opportunity for students to have the kind of deep learning experiences that mirror professional practice and problem solving." The authors further noted the traditional engineering education model "with its attendant deductive teaching strategies, structured problems, demonstrations, and assessments of student learning does not reflect what the significant and compelling body of research on learning suggests about how students learn and develop and how experts are formed."

The need is especially acute in today's world, with its rapid and exponential growth in knowledge in all fields of engineering and others areas. The major challenge facing all educators is to satisfy the engineers' growing need to utilise and integrate material from different sources and disciplines (McCowan and Knapper, 2002).

This is certainly true for our modular approach to teaching, where chemical engineering principles are slotted into different core modules, and students are often told to learn a module because "the concepts will be useful to you later when you do your final year project." Humphreys et al (1981) summed up the attitude well, when they noted:

"It is taken for granted, apparently, that in time students will see for themselves how things fit together. Unfortunately, the reality of the situation is that they tend to learn what we teach. If we teach connectedness and integration, they learn that. If we teach separation and discontinuity, that is what they learn. To suppose otherwise would be incongruous.(p.xi)".

Froyd and Ohland (2005) criticised the modular teaching, noting that: "Questions have been repeatedly raised about whether neatly compartmentalized courses can provide learning activities that stimulate, encourage, and enable students to structure their knowledge across course and disciplinary boundaries".

There is therefore strong impetus to integrate the various subjects taught in separate modules. Bordogna et al (1993) in particular, argued that "engineering is an integrative process and thus engineering education, should be designed toward that end." The authors further noted that "there is a need to focus on creating a *holistic* education for students, particularly undergraduate students, because engineering's core as a profession lies in integrating *all* knowledge to some purpose". Lipson et al (1993) posits that "an enduring argument for integration is that it represents a way to avoid the fragmented and irrelevant acquisition of isolated facts, transforming knowledge into personally useful tools for learning new information".

Fogarty (1991) has described ten levels of curricula integration ranging from integration within discipline ("fragmented", "connected" and "nested") to across several disciplines ("sequenced", "shared", "webbed", "threaded" and "integrated") to within and across learners ("immersed" and "networked"). Advantages and disadvantages of integrated curriculum had been discussed by various authors, e.g. Al-Holou et al (1999), Everett et al (2000) and Bandaranayahe (2011). Various educators who introduced integrated curriculum attested to its effectiveness in helping students learnt better, with some even claimed that it helped student retention (Froyd and Ohland, 2005; Lipson et al, 1993; Jackson, 2001; McCowan and Knapper, 2002; McCarthy et al, 2011). Looking at curriculum integration from students Laughlin et al (2007) identified three factors affecting students' perceived level of integration: (1) the connections made by students among mathematics, physics, and engineering design classes; (2) the students' perceived level of communication, cooperation, and synergy between faculty teaching the above three classes; and (3) the level of perceived faculty involvement in students' learning experiences. The authors reported a positive relationship between the extent to which students perceived integration and the extent to which integration contributed to a positive learning experience.

The verdict is best summed up by Drake & Reid (2010), who stated: "Research has consistently shown that students in integrated programs demonstrate academic performance equal to, or better than, students in discipline-based programs. In addition, students are

more engaged in school, and less prone to attendance and behavior problems.”

Despite the stated benefits of integrated curriculum, objections abound. Perhaps the most “passionate” criticism against integrated curriculum comes from George (1996) who claimed that all the accolades about integrated curriculum are “unfounded, unsubstantiated, or both.” He concluded that little evidence exists to show that integrated curriculum is more effective than good teaching of a traditional curriculum. His advice was “IC advocates continue to clarify the meaning of the term; conduct and publish credible research on IC results; and realize and appreciate the dedication and commitment of the thousands of educators not yet persuaded about wholesale, immediate IC adoption.” However, as noted by Simanu-Klutz (1997): “Although at first glance, this may appear to be a doom-and-gloom attack on integrated curriculum, his admonishment should be seen as an invitation for teachers and administrators to understand this approach more thoroughly and to study it carefully”. Rennie et al (2005) opined that evidence about the impact of integrated programs on student learning is not easily identified in the literature because of the difficulty researchers have finding a common way of viewing ‘learning’. Their own work has demonstrated that the kind of learning documented can be different depending on the theoretical perspective the researchers adopt.

Curriculum Integration in Chemical Engineering

Prior to CDIO, project-based integration, *Final Year Project (FYP)* is the *de facto* approach to curriculum integration, which all graduating (i.e. Year 3) our students are required to complete. Our students are also required to complete another project entitled *Plant Design Project*, also in year 3, which is often referred to as the “capstone” project. There is also limited integration between mathematics and sciences (namely chemistry and biology) with the technical topics in chemical engineering. While these approaches remain important, we have introduced various other means to promote curriculum integration after adoption of CDIO.

McKenna et al (2001) challenged the conventional approach of curriculum integration efforts, which is “based on a common-sense assumption that an integrated curriculum is beneficial to student learning and will lead to a more integrative understanding of the discipline”. They do not take for granted that integration of the curriculum results in improved student learning, but seek to empirically explore the effects that integrative changes have on student learning. We could not have agreed more! We were also once guilty of such mind set: that by Year 3 students are able to utilize what they learnt over the first two years effectively in completing their capstone projects. However, the modular approach in our teaching system often leads to difficulties; and students are often told to learn a module because “the concepts will be useful to you later when you do your final year project.” Such an approach is now incompatible with today’s learners, leading to

reduced interest in studying engineering, and subsequent in pursuing an engineering career.

With CDIO, we adopted the practice-oriented approach, to design learning tasks that simulated real-world work environment. Indeed Sheppard et al (2008) advocated: “If engineering students are to be prepared to meet the challenges of today and tomorrow, the center of their education should be professional practice, integrating technical knowledge and skills of practice through a consistent focus on developing the identity and commitment of the professional engineer. Teaching for professional practice should be the touchstone for future choices about both curriculum content and pedagogical strategies in undergraduate engineering education. The ability to make connections, to solve problems by looking at multiple perspectives, and to incorporate information from different fields, will be an essential ingredient for success in the future.”

Presently, our integrated curriculum comprises the following approaches:

- (1) Integration of technical knowledge across different disciplines, e.g. mathematics and sciences in chemical engineering, mostly in Year 1 and Year 2
- (2) Integration via capstone projects: *Final Year Project* and *Plant Design Project*, both in Year 3
- (3) Integration of C-D-I-O skills (skills in conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating an engineering product, process or system) across all three years. This approach is aimed mainly at supporting our *Final Year Project*
- (4) Integration of “generic” CDIO skills (such as communication, teamwork, critical thinking, etc) in selected core modules across all three years

The following sections provided short discussions of the challenges faced in current approaches that lead to a need to step up the effort in this important area.

Curriculum Integration via Plant Design Project

In the design project, students working in groups are required to carry out a conceptual design (using computer modelling and simulation) of a chemical plant to produce a given product of specified purity and production rate (see for example, von Solms et al 2010).

Prior to CDIO, *Plant Design Project* was a standalone Year 3 module, with another basic module on process design (namely modelling and simulation) taught in another standalone module in Year 2. After CDIO, we integrate process design into the curriculum – consistent with the trends in chemical engineering education worldwide, which is often known as the “vertical integration” of design in the chemical engineering community (Hirt, 1998; Gatehouse et al, 1999; Shaeiwitz, 2001; Yargeau, 2005). This project is now embedded in a Year 3 module *Plant Design, Economics and Sustainable Development*.

A potential pedagogical drawback for this approach towards curriculum integration arises from the “unique” feature of such a design project, in that the physical chemical plant is never actually built! In this sense

“capstone” project in chemical engineering is quite different from similarly-named projects for other disciplines, e.g. mechanical engineering. It is therefore possible for students to successfully construct and use models without really understanding the physical phenomena within each unit operations that made up the complete process plant (Dahm, 2002). Indeed, often we find students to focus too much on getting the simulation program to converge, by trying different process parameters instead of interpreting the error messages to understand why the program failed to converge in the first place.

Also, what is really lacking in this approach is the lack of realism of chemical engineering practice. Some institutions tried to inject more realism into such projects by requiring students to work on real-world process design, some with industrial partners (see for example Counce et al, 2001). However, at the diploma-level, due to time constraint and knowledge level of the students, the project is scoped such that there would not be sufficient depth to carry out the sort of rigorous analysis as in the university degree programs. We did not engage industry partners although the project brief is still based on real-world chemical plants.

Curriculum Integration via Final Year Project

The student *Final Year Project (FYP)* is another platform to achieve curriculum integration. The *FYP* is closer to the CDIO Design-Implement Experience (Standard 5) in terms of offering hands-on opportunity for students with a product and/or process as the deliverable. However, we felt that relying on *FYPs* to achieve the objectives of curriculum integration is inadequate, and over the years had noted some problems with this approach:

- (1) All projects are different. Our students can take up projects of such diversity ranging from feasibility study, to applied research and experimentation, to pilot-testing, to process plant design and optimization. The wide nature of projects that DCHE students can undertake hence posed challenges to ensure the same learning outcomes for all students.
- (2) Related to the above, often a project will last a few years, with each cohort of students working on individual phases of C-D-I-O towards final completion. The same cohort of students rarely followed through a project from inception to completion.
- (3) Also, depending on the nature of the projects, not all learning outcomes can be covered within the given project. For example, a project on feasibility study on certain species of algae to produce biofuels, will not engage students directly in troubleshooting a fixed-bed chemical reactor typical in an oil refinery.

Curriculum Integration among Core Modules

In these integration efforts, we first use the Year 1 module *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*, consistent with CDIO Standard 4, as the “anchor”

module for that serves as an introductory-level integration effort. This module exposes students to basic understanding of the following topics, which were later fully elaborated in various core modules throughout the three-years of study:

- Unit operations and equipment typical in the chemical processing industry
- Roles and responsibilities of chemical engineers, including the need for sustainable development
- Teamwork and communication, personal skills and attitudes (creative and critical thinking, etc)
- Ethics and global mindset

For the rest of other core modules, we mostly carried out the integration in the laboratory components of these modules, for example, *Chemical Engineering Principles and Simulation* (Year 1), *Heat Transfer and Equipment* (Year 2), *Rotating Equipment* (Year 2), *Chemical Reaction Engineering* (Year 3), *Separation Processes* (Year 3) etc. In these modules, we “cross-linked” suitable topics from relevant modules into each of the core module. Details of these efforts had been presented at various CDIO conferences (see for example, [32]).

We found that this approach, while successfully implemented in the curriculum through various laboratory activities, are still somewhat limited in terms of its coverage as these tended to be dominated by the subject matter in the core module. During the above re-designing activities we noted that several concepts repeated appeared in various learning tasks in all years of study: SHE (safety, health and environment), and instrumentation and control. Hence, there exist an opportunity for us to achieve more curriculum integration. This will take the form of engineering practice, as briefly explained in the next section.

Curriculum Integration via Engineering Practice

The discussion of what is meant by “engineering practice” is presented by the first author elsewhere (Cheah, 2013). With this approach, we firstly identified core modules that are more “integrative” in nature, whereby their applications cut across other more technical core modules. These modules are: *Environmental Engineering*, *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention*; and *Process Instrumentation & Control* (see Figure 1). We then re-design the learning tasks in these modules to introduce elements of engineering practice that offers the opportunity to achieve the dual purpose of firstly in strengthening curriculum integration across modules and secondly in making learning the module more meaningful, by through greater appreciation of the type of work performed in the chemical engineering profession. This will enhance the students’ learning experience not just in the subject but also chemical engineering as a whole.

Issues and Challenges; Moving Ahead

We had successfully piloted with the module *Process Instrumentation & Control* which is described

elsewhere (Koh and Cheah, 2013). We are making plans to revamp other two modules as well. This entails some re-organization of the course structure and also new integrated pilot plants. The latter may entail some financial burden at times of limited budget. We also anticipated that this approach may entail the use of new pedagogy, e.g. problem-based learning, which works better with small class sizes and thus represents potential challenge in terms of faculty manpower. In addition, many faculty also need training to acquaint themselves with PBL, which is not the “mainstream” in chemical engineering education. Other challenges include evaluation and assessment, for example in terms of transferability of knowledge and skills, which may necessitate use of new approaches, such as concept maps or integrated examination questions. Lastly, we need to carry out student surveys to ascertain their learning experiences and effectiveness of our curriculum integration effort.

Figure 1. Curriculum Integration in Chemical Engineering via “Integrative” Modules

Conclusions

The general approaches toward curriculum integration have been presented. We hope that by making learning more meaningful in the course; we can achieve “teaching for transfer and thoughtful learning” that Perkins (1991) advocated:

“A concern with connecting things up, with integrating ideas, within and across subject matters, and with elements of out-of-school life, inherently is a concern with understanding in a broader and a deeper sense. Accordingly there is a natural alliance between those making a special effort to teach for understanding and those making a special effort toward integrative education.”

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